

SIROP

LOD-GEOSS

Open Energy Platform

Publication of FAIR Data and Metadata

Part 1: Open Energy Metadata and Data Annotations

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Open Energy Family

Open Energy Family

Open Energy Metadata

- A Metadata Standard for energy data
- Based on established technologies und standards
- Latest version (v1.5.3) is “ontology ready”

<https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/oemetadata>

FRictionless
DATA

Categories

- **General** (name, title, description)
- **Context** (homepage, funding, contact)
- **Spatial** (location, extent, resolution)
- **Temporal** (referenceDate, timeseries)
- **Source** (origin, licenses)
- **Provenience** (contributors)
- **Resource** (fields, type, description)
- **Review** (context and badge)

➤ ~ 70 keys

Prioritisation

- **Iron** – Technically required for data structure
-
- **Bronze** – Basic description of the data
 - **Silver** – Supplement description of the data
 - **Gold** – Extended description of the context
 - **Platinum** – Ontological annotation

Open Energy Metadata - Example

Danish Energy Agency

OUR RESPONSIBILITIES OUR SERVICES ABOUT US PRESS Q DA

Technology Data for Generation of Electricity and District Heating

This Technology Data catalogue includes technology data for technologies for centralized and decentralized production of electricity and district heat. Technology data concerns more or less mature technologies.

Home > Our Services > Projections and models > Technology Data > Technology Data for Generation of Electricity and ...

There is currently one combined Technology Data catalogue concerning generation of electricity and district heating. The catalogue was first published in August 2016, and is updated continuously. Technology descriptions in the previous catalogue from May 2012 have now been included in the catalogue from 2016 although some are not updated since 2015. It is mentioned in the beginning of the specific chapters, when each technology has been updated the last time.

<https://ens.dk/en/our-services/projections-and-models/technology-data/technology-data-generation-electricity-and>

Open Energy Metadata - Example

Data sheets

Technology	20 Large wind turbines on land										Note	Ref	
	2015	2020	2030	2040	2050	Uncertainty (2020)		Uncertainty (2050)					
Year of final investment decision						Lower	Upper	Lower	Upper				
Energy/technical data													
Generating capacity for one unit (MW)	3,1	4,2	5	5,5	6	2,0	6,0	1,5	8,0	A1	3		
Average annual full-load hours	3100	3400	3600	3700	3800	2000	4000	2000	4500	A, L	3		
Forced outage (%)	3,0%	2,5%	2,0%	1,8%	1,5%	1,0%	5,0%	1,0%	5,0%	B	4		
Planned outage (%)	0,3%	0,3%	0,3%	0,3%	0,3%	0,1%	0,5%	0,1%	0,5%	C	4		
Technical lifetime (years)	25	27	30	30	30	25	35	25	40	D	14		
Construction time (years)	1,5	1,5	1,5	1,5	1,5	1	3	1	3	E	4		
Space requirement (1000m2/MW)	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	F			
Regulation ability													
Primary regulation (% per 30 seconds)										G			
Secondary regulation (% per minute)										G			
Financial data (in 2015€)													
Nominal investment (M€/MW)	1,33	1,12	1,04	0,98	0,96	0,77	1,16	0,80	1,19		16, 2, 4		
- of which equipment	0,89	0,71	0,64	0,59	0,58	0,57	0,86	0,46	0,69		25		
- of which installation/development	0,12	0,09	0,08	0,08	0,07	0,07	0,11	0,06	0,09		25		
- of which is related to grid connection	0,06	0,05	0,05	0,05	0,05	0,04	0,06	0,04	0,06		25		
- of which is related to rent of land	0,09	0,09	0,09	0,09	0,09	0,07	0,10	0,07	0,10		25		
- of which is related to decommissioning of existing turbines	0,04	0,04	0,04	0,04	0,04	0,03	0,04	0,03	0,04		25		
- of which is related to other costs (i.e. compensation of neighbours, etc.)	0,13	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,11	0,17	0,11	0,17	I	25, 26		
Fixed O&M (€/MW/year)	25.600	14.000	12.600	11.592	11.340	11.200	16.800	9.072	13.608	I	25, 26		
Variable O&M (€/MWh)	2,80	1,50	1,35	1,24	1,22	1,20	1,80	0,97	1,46				
Technology specific data													
Rotor diameter	106	130	145	155	165	90	130	100	150	K	4, 26		
Hub height	85	85	100	105	110	85	120	85	150		4, 26		
Specific power (W/m2)	351	316	303	291	281	314	452	191	453				
Average capacity factor	35%	39%	41%	42%	43%	23%	46%	23%	51%		4, 26		
Average availability (%)	97%	97%	98%	98%	98%	99%	95%	99%	95%		4, 26		

Excel

Onshore wind turbine, utility - renewable power - wind - large											-	-
2015	2020	2030	2040	2050	2020	2050	2020	2050	2020	2050		
ctrl	ctrl	ctrl	ctrl	ctrl	lower	upper	lower	upper	lower	upper	note	ref
Energy/technical data												
Generating capacity for one unit [MW_e]	3.1	4.2	5	5.5	6	2	6	1.5	8	A1	3	
Forced outage []	3%	3%	2%	2%	2%	1%	5%	1%	5%	B	4	
Planned outage [weeks per year]	0.16	0.16	0.16	0.16	0.16	0.05	0.26	0.05	0.26	C	4	
Technical lifetime [years]	25	27	30	30	30	25	35	25	40	D	14	
Construction time [years]	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1	3	1	3	E	4	
Space requirement [1000 m2/MW_e]										F		
Regulation ability												
Primary regulation [of full load, per 30 seconds] []										G		
Secondary regulation [of full load, per minute] []										G		
Financial data												
Nominal investment (*total) [2015-MEUR/MW_e]	1.33	1.12	1.04	0.98	0.96	0.77	1.16	0.8	1.19		[16, 2, 4]	
Nominal investment (equipment) [2015-MEUR/MW_e]	0.89	0.71	0.64	0.59	0.58	0.57	0.86	0.46	0.69		25	
Nominal investment (installation) [2015-MEUR/MW_e]	0.12	0.09	0.08	0.08	0.07	0.07	0.11	0.06	0.09	M	25	
Nominal investment (decommissioning of existing turbines) [2015-MEUR/MW_e]	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.03	0.04	0.03	0.04		25	
Nominal investment (grid connection) [2015-MEUR/MW_e]	0.06	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.04	0.06	0.04		25	
Nominal investment (other, i.e. compensation of neighbours) [2015-MEUR/MW_e]	0.13	0.14	0.14	0.14	0.14	0.11	0.17	0.11	0.17	I	[25, 26]	
Nominal investment (land rent) [2015-MEUR/MW_e]	0.09	0.09	0.09	0.09	0.09	0.07	0.1	0.07	0.1		25	
Variable O&M (*total) [2015-EUR/MWh_e]	2.8	1.5	1.35	1.24	1.22	1.2	1.8	0.97	1.46			
Fixed O&M (*total) [2015-EUR/MW_e/y]	25600	14000	12600	11592	11340	11200	16800	9072	13608	I	[25, 26]	
Technology-specific data												
Availability []	97%	97%	98%	98%	98%	99%	95%	99%	95%			
Hub height [m]	85	85	100	105	110	85	120	85	150		[4, 26]	
Rotor diameter [m]	106	130	145	155	165	90	130	100	150	K	[4, 26]	
Specific power [W_e/m2]	351.29	316.43	302.79	291.48	280.6	314.38	452.04	190.99	452.71			
Average capacity factor []	35%	39%	41%	42%	43%	23%	46%	23%	51%		[4, 26]	
Average annual full-load hours [MWh_e/MW_e]	3100	3400	3600	3700	3800	2000	4000	2000	4500	[A, L]	3	
Notes:												
A1. The capacity is set to 3.5 MW in 2015 and 2020 based on data of current wind turbines and under the anticipation that the maximum height will not exceed 150m before 2020. From 2030 a slight increase in generator size and hub height is assumed, where the effect of expected removal of present max. 150m tip height.												
A. The full load hours (annual production [MWh] per installed power [MW]) depending on the actual location of the wind farm, wake losses and technological characteristics of the individual turbine. The value is an average for the expected locations of the wind farms.												
B. Modern turbines has typically higher forced outage than older smaller turbines had when they were newer due to more complex technology.												
C. Planned outage is typically 1-2 service visits a year, with a maximum duration of one work day, but there can also be planned outage due to shadow flicker stop or sector management (protect turbines at given wind direction).												
D. The life time depends on the wind conditions, average annual speed and turbulence, relative to the design class of the turbine.												
E. The construction time is the period from FID to commissioning. But from first "dig" to turbines are in operation less than 1/2 year is needed for smaller wind farms (clusters), where the similar period for larger wind farms is needed.												
F. An area of around 50 m x 50 m is needed for a modern wind turbine. Another way of defining the "area use" could be the noise zone, which ranges up to 600-800 m from the wind turbine in worst case.												
G. Wind turbines can be downward regulated within very short time and can therefore (if the wind is blowing) be used in both the primary and secondary downward regulation.												
H. 2015 investment costs are based on a number of prospects for projects published in relation to Køberetsordningen. 2020 investment costs are based on updated data from Køberetsordningen. Note that the investment costs are assumed to be 75% of the total yearly O&M costs are assumed to be fixed cost and 25% are assumed to be variable cost.												
I. Currently only turbines up to 150 m total height is installed commercially in Denmark because of strict demands to higher turbines. No change in the national regulation is assumed until after 2020. Some test sites are expected to be installed after 2020.												
J. It is expected that the production (FLH) increase 13% from 2015 to 2020 and 3% from 2020-2030 and 1% per decade from 2030-2050.												
K. Includes development cost.												
L. Subscript abbreviations used in the datasheets: input = _i, electricity production = _e, heat production = _h												
M. The empty square brackets [] denote parameters expressed in terms of a proportion. The raw data is in the raw decimal form, but note that these values are formatted as percentage in the wide report tables for readability.												
References:												
2. DTU International Energy Report - Wind Energy, DTU, 2014												
3. Master data register of wind turbines at end of December 2014, Danish Energy Agency, 2015												
4. Nielsen, P. et al., Vindmøllers økonomi EUDP projekt 33033-0196, 2010												
Information from EnergyDK based on analyses of installed projects (2015-24), published under "Køberetsordningen", 2025												

Notes:

- A The capacity is set to 3.5 MW in 2015 and 2020 based on data of current wind turbines and under the anticipation that the maximum height will not exceed 150m before 2020. From 2030 a slight increase in generator size, and hub height is assumed, where the effect of expected removal of present max. 150m tip height.
- A The full load hours (annual production [MWh] per installed power [MW]) depending on the actual location of the wind farm, wake losses and technological characteristics of the individual turbine. The value is an average for the expected locations of the wind farms. FLH also depends on wake losses, noise reduction and technological characteristics of the individual turbine. The level for 2020 is based on expectations from the November 18 auction winners locations and the 2019 preferred technology choice. For 2030 and 2050 a slight increase is assumed based on decrease in specific power and increase in hub height.
- B Modern turbines has typically higher forced outage than older smaller turbines had when they were newer due to more complex technology.

https://ens.dk/sites/ens.dk/files/Analyser/technology_data_catalogue_for_el_and_dh.pdf
https://ens.dk/sites/ens.dk/files/Analyser/technology_data_for_el_and_dh.xlsx

Open Energy Metadata - Example

Challenges of energy data:

1. Open data license
2. Data structures not machine readable
3. Mixture of data and metadata
4. Link to a controlled vocabulary (ontology)

Open Energy Metadata - Example

General Keys

Meta Information i

[Download JSON](#) [Edit](#)

Name	rli_dea_td_generation_wind_turbine
Title	RLI - Danish Energy Agency - Technology Data for Generation of Electricity and District Heating - Technology Data Catalogue for Electricity and district heating production - Updated April 2020 - Wind Turbine (Selected Parameter)
Id	http://openenergyplatform.org/dataedit/view/model_draft/rli_dea_td_generation_wind_turbine
Description	This Technology Data catalogue includes technology data for technologies for centralized and decentralized production of electricity and district heat. Technology data concerns more or less mature technologies. There is currently one combined Technology Data catalogue concerning generation of electricity and district heating. The catalogue was first published in August 2016, and is updated continuously. Technology descriptions in the previous catalogue from May 2012 have now been included in the catalogue from 2016 although some are not updated since 2015. It is mentioned in the beginning of the specific chapters, when each technology has been updated the last time. Index: 20 Wind turbines on-shore (updated May 2019) On-shore turbines and Domestic turbines. 21 Wind turbines off-shore (updated May 2019) Off-shore turbines and Near shore turbines (minor adjustment September 2019).

https://openenergy-platform.org/dataedit/view/model_draft/rli_dea_td_generation_wind_turbine

Open Energy Metadata - Example

Subject wind energy converting unit

- **Name:** wind energy converting unit
- **Path:** https://openenergy-platform.org/ontology/oeo/OEO_00000044

Keywords

- RLI
- Danish Energy Agency
- Technology Data Catalogue
- Wind
- Review
- CC-BY-4.0

PublicationDate 2022-02-11

Open Energy Metadata - Example

Context

- **Homepage:** <https://reiner-lemoine-institut.de/lod-geoss/>
- **SourceCode:** <https://github.com/LOD-GEOSS>
- **Contact:** <https://github.com/Ludee>
- **GrantNo:** 03EI1005D
- **FundingAgency:** Bundesministerium für Wirtschaft und Klimaschutz
- **FundingAgencyLogo:** https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:BMW_Logo_2021.svg#/media/File:BMW_Logo_2021.svg
- **PublisherLogo:** <https://reiner-lemoine-institut.de/wp-content/uploads/2015/09/rliologo.png>

https://openenergy-platform.org/dataedit/view/model_draft/rli_dea_td_generation_wind_turbine

Open Energy Metadata - Example

Spatial	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Extent: Europe
Temporal	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• ReferenceDate: 2015-01-01• Timeseries: timeseries element<ul style="list-style-type: none">◦ Start: 2015-10-05T00:◦ End: 2050-10-05T00:◦ Resolution: 10 years
Review	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Path: https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/data-preprocessing/issues/92• Badge: Platinum
Language	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• en-GB

https://openenergy-platform.org/dataedit/view/model_draft/rli_dea_td_generation_wind_turbine

Open Energy Metadata - Example

Sources

Homepage

PDF

Excel

Danish Energy Agency - Technology Data

- **Title:** Danish Energy Agency - Technology Data
- **Description:** The Danish Energy Agency and Energinet publish catalogues of technology data for energy technologies. Technology Data provides information about technology, economy and environment for a number of energy installations and are among other things used by the Danish Energy Agency for energy projections.
- **Path:** <https://ens.dk/en/our-services/projections-and-models/technology-data>
- **Licenses:**
Null
 - **Attribution:** © Danish Energy Agency 2021
 - **Name:** Null

Danish Energy Agency - Technology Data for Generation of Electricity and District Heating

- **Title:** Danish Energy Agency - Technology Data for Generation of Electricity and District Heating
- **Description:** TThis Technology Data catalogue includes technology data for technologies for centralized and decentralized production of electricity and district heat. Technology data concerns more or less mature technologies.
- **Path:** <https://ens.dk/en/our-services/projections-and-models/technology-data/technology-data-generation-electricity-and>
- **Licenses:**
Null
 - **Attribution:** © Danish Energy Agency 2021
 - **Name:** Null

Technology Data Catalogue for Electricity and district heating production - Updated April 2020

- **Title:** Technology Data Catalogue for Electricity and district heating production - Updated April 2020
- **Description:** Data collection for electricity generation and district heating plants, last update: April 2020
- **Path:** https://ens.dk/sites/ens.dk/files/Analyser/technology_data_for_el_and_dh.xlsx
- **Licenses:**
Null
 - **Attribution:** © Danish Energy Agency 2021
 - **Name:** Null

https://openenergy-platform.org/dataedit/view/model_draft/rli_dea_td_generation_wind_turbine

Open Energy Metadata - Example

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- **Attribution:** © Danish Energy Agency © Reiner Lemoine Institut
- **Name:** CC-BY-4.0
- **Title:** Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International
- **Path:** <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/legalcode>

Challenge 1: Open data license ✓

https://openenergy-platform.org/dataedit/view/model_draft/rli_dea_td_generation_wind_turbine

Open Energy Metadata - Example

Contributors

Christoph Muschner

- **Title:** Christoph Muschner
- **Email:** christoph.muschner@rl-institut.de
- **Object:** metadata
- **Comment:** Transpose the original table
- **Date:** 2021-06-29

Ludee

- **Title:** Ludee
- **Email:** datenzentrum@rl-institut.de
- **Object:** metadata
- **Comment:** Create table with updated data structure
- **Date:** 2022-02-11

Ludee

- **Title:** Ludee
- **Email:** datenzentrum@rl-institut.de
- **Object:** metadata
- **Comment:** Update to OEMetadata version 1.5.0
- **Date:** 2022-02-11

Ludee

- **Title:** Ludee
- **Email:** datenzentrum@rl-institut.de
- **Object:** metadata
- **Comment:** Update to OEMetadata version 1.5.1
- **Date:** 2022-02-15

Ludee

- **Title:** Ludee
- **Email:** datenzentrum@rl-institut.de
- **Object:** metadata
- **Comment:** Add data annotation
- **Date:** 2022-10-04

https://openenergy-platform.org/dataedit/view/model_draft/rli_dea_td_generation_wind_turbine

Open Energy Metadata - Example

Resources	model_draft.rli_dea_td_generation_wind_turbine
	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Profile: tabular-data-resource• Name: model_draft.rli_dea_td_generation_wind_turbine• Path: https://openenergy-platform.org/dataedit/view/model_draft/rli_dea_td_generation_wind_turbine• Format: PostgreSQL• Encoding: UTF-8• Schema:<ul style="list-style-type: none">◦ PrimaryKey:<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ id◦ ForeignKeys:<p>There is no valid entry for this field</p>◦ Fields:<ul style="list-style-type: none">id<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Name: id▪ Description: Unique identifier▪ Type: serial▪ Is_about:<p>There is no valid entry for this field</p>▪ Value_reference:<p>There is no valid entry for this field</p>
	model <ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Name: model▪ Description: Model name▪ Type: text▪ Is_about:<p>There is no valid entry for this field</p>▪ Value_reference:<p>There is no valid entry for this field</p>

https://openenergy-platform.org/dataedit/view/model_draft/rli_dea_td_generation_wind_turbine

Open Energy Metadata - Example

generating_capacity

- **Name:** generating_capacity
- **Description:** Generation capacity for one unit of the technology
- **Type:** real
- **Unit:** MW

full_load_hours

- **Name:** full_load_hours
- **Description:** Average annual full load hours of the technology
- **Type:** integer
- **Unit:** h

nominal_investment

- **Name:** nominal_investment
- **Description:** Nominal investment of the technology
- **Type:** real
- **Unit:** M€/MW

rotor_diameter

- **Name:** rotor_diameter
- **Description:** Rotor diameter of the wind turbine
- **Type:** integer
- **Unit:** m

https://openenergy-platform.org/dataedit/view/model_draft/rli_dea_td_generation_wind_turbine

Open Energy Metadata - Example

Dataset (Table)

id	model	scenario	region	type	year	generating_capacity	full_load_hours	nominal_investment	rotor_diameter	hub_height
1	dea_technology_data_generation	wind_turbine_2015	Europe	onshore	2015	3.1	3100	1.326	106	85
2	dea_technology_data_generation	wind_turbine_2020	Europe	onshore	2020	4.2	3400	1.119	130	85
3	dea_technology_data_generation	wind_turbine_2030	Europe	onshore	2030	5	3600	1.036	145	100
4	dea_technology_data_generation	wind_turbine_2040	Europe	onshore	2040	5.5	3700	0.978	155	105
5	dea_technology_data_generation	wind_turbine_2050	Europe	onshore	2050	6	3800	0.963	165	110
6	dea_technology_data_generation	wind_turbine_2020_uncertainty_lower	Europe	onshore	2020	2	2000	0.77	90	85
7	dea_technology_data_generation	wind_turbine_2020_uncertainty_upper	Europe	onshore	2020	6	4000	1.156	130	120
8	dea_technology_data_generation	wind_turbine_2050_uncertainty_lower	Europe	onshore	2050	1.5	2000	0.796	100	85
9	dea_technology_data_generation	wind_turbine_2050_uncertainty_upper	Europe	onshore	2050	8	4500	1.193	150	150
10	dea_technology_data_generation	wind_turbine_2015	Europe	offshore	2015	8	4400	2.86	164	103
11	dea_technology_data_generation	wind_turbine_2020	Europe	offshore	2020	10	4500	2.128	190	115
12	dea_technology_data_generation	wind_turbine_2030	Europe	offshore	2030	15	4650	1.935	235	135
13	dea_technology_data_generation	wind_turbine_2040	Europe	offshore	2040	18	4700	1.809	260	150
14	dea_technology_data_generation	wind_turbine_2050	Europe	offshore	2050	20	4900	1.777	280	160
15	dea_technology_data_generation	wind_turbine_2020_uncertainty_lower	Europe	offshore	2020	8	4200	1.916		
16	dea_technology_data_generation	wind_turbine_2020_uncertainty_upper	Europe	offshore	2020	12	5000	2.235		
17	dea_technology_data_generation	wind_turbine_2050_uncertainty_lower	Europe	offshore	2050	10	4500	1.422		
18	dea_technology_data_generation	wind_turbine_2050_uncertainty_upper	Europe	offshore	2050	30	5500	1.955		

Showing 1 to 18 of 18 entries

Previous 1 Next

Challenge 2: Data structures not machine readable ✓
Challenge 3: Mixture of data and metadata ✓

Open Energy Metadata - Example

- **Name:** year
- **Description:** Reference year
- **Type:** integer
- **Is_about:**
year
 - **Name:** year
 - **Path:** https://openenergy-platform.org/ontology/oeo/UO_0000036

Class label: year

Definition:

A time unit which is equal to 12 months which in science is taken to be equal to 365.25 days.

Super classes:

time unit

view

https://openenergy-platform.org/ontology/oeo/UO_0000036

Open Energy Metadata - Example

generating_capacity

- **Name:** generating_capacity
- **Description:** Generation capacity for one unit of the technology
- **Type:** real
- **Is_about:**

declared net capacity

- **Name:** declared net capacity
- **Path:** https://openenergy-platform.org/ontology/oeo/OEO_00230002
- **Unit:** MW

Class label: declared net capacity

Definition:

Declared net capacity is a power capacity stating the maximum power a power generating unit or a power plant can deliver to the electrical grid. It equals the sum of the rated powers of all plant generators minus all power used internally within the plant.

Sub classes:

block size

view

Super classes:

power capacity

view

https://openenergy-platform.org/ontology/oeo/OEO_00230002

Open Energy Metadata - Example

type

- **Name:** type
- **Description:** Type of wind turbine
- **Type:** text
- **Value_reference:**

onshore wind farm

- **Value:** onshore
- **Name:** onshore wind farm
- **Path:** https://openenergy-platform.org/ontology/oeo/OEO_00000311

offshore wind farm

- **Value:** offshore
- **Name:** offshore wind farm
- **Path:** https://openenergy-platform.org/ontology/oeo/OEO_00000308

Class label: onshore wind farm

Definition:

An onshore wind farm is a wind farm that is build on land.

Class label: offshore wind farm

Definition:

An offshore wind farm is a wind farm that is build in a body of water, usually the ocean.

Super classes:

wind farm

view

https://openenergy-platform.org/ontology/oeo/OEO_00000447

Challenge 4: Link to ontology ✓

Summary:

- A flexible and comprehensive Metadata Standard
- Simple format and handling (JSON)
- Used and improved by an active community
- Links to ontologies possible
- High-Scores at FAIR und 5 Stars LOD

„The opposite of **‘open’** isn’t **‘closed’**. The opposite of **‘open’** is **‘broken’**.“

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